

**THE SYNTHESIS OF EASTERN AND WESTERN THOUGHT IN POOLA
TIRUPATI RAJU'S COMPARATIVE PHILOSOPHY
СИНТЕЗ ВОСТОЧНОЙ И ЗАПАДНОЙ МЫСЛИ В
КОМПАРАТИВИСТСКОЙ ФИЛОСОФИИ ПУЛЫ ТИРУПАТИ РАДЖУ
POOLA TIRUPATI RAJUNING QIYOSIY FALSAFASIDA SHARQ VA
G‘ARB TAFAKKURI SINTEZI**

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Annotation: This thesis focuses on Poola Tirupati Raju’s unique and innovative integration of Eastern and Western philosophies. In a world that is rapidly becoming polarized, Raju’s comparative approach provides a way of synthesizing two opposing ways of thinking. This work is focused on revealing the interdependence of human beings regardless of the culture they belong to, thus expanding the concept of philosophy. Thus, by analysing the steps of his approach, this thesis aims to underline the relevance of Raju’s ideas in fostering a rich philosophical conversation across the world.

Key words: integration, traditions, cross-cultural, irrational, spiritualistic, mysticism, existentialism.

Аннотация: Данная работа посвящена уникальной и инновационной интеграции восточной и западной философий в трудах Пулы Тирупати Раджу. В мире, который стремительно поляризуется, компаративистский подход Раджу предлагает способ синтеза двух противоположных типов мышления. Работа направлена на раскрытие взаимозависимости людей, независимо от их

культурной принадлежности, тем самым расширяя концепцию философии. Анализируя шаги его подхода, данная работа подчеркивает актуальность идей Раджу в содействии богатому философскому диалогу по всему миру.

Ключевые слова: интеграция, традиции, межкультурный, иррациональный, спиритуалистический, феноменология, экзистенциализм.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezis Poola Tirupati Rajuning sharq va g'arb falsafalarini noyob va innovatsion tarzda uyg'unlashtirishga bag'ishlangan. Tez sur'atlarda qutblanib borayotgan dunyoda Rajuning qiyosiy yondashuvi ikkita qarama-qarshi fikrlash tizimini sintez qilish usulini taklif etadi. Ushbu ish insonlarning madaniyati qaysi bo'lmasin, ularning o'zaro bog'liqligini ochib berishga qaratilgan bo'lib, falsafa tushunchasini kengaytiradi. Shu bilan birga, uning yondashuvi bosqichlarini tahlil qilib, mazkur Radju g'oyalari jahon bo'ylab boy falsafiy muloqotni rivojlantirishda qanchalik ahamiyatli ekanligini ko'rsatishni maqsad qilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: integratsiya, an'analar, madaniyatlararo, irratsional, spiritualistik, mistitsizm, ekzistensializm.

Introduction. In a world where the distinctions between countries and political systems are fading, one can feel the tension between the irresistible forces of East and West — those two great thought systems that murmur in the human mind from two opposite ends. The East, wrapped in the shroud of mysticism, longs for the oneness, for the annihilation of the individual in the cosmos. The West is arrogant and rebellious, it is alone in its egoism, creating its world with science, with reason. But there is a need, a necessity perhaps, to connect these two directions – this is what Poola Tirupati Raju perhaps realized better than anyone. He did not just look at the division. He felt it, as one feels the cold wind rushing through a narrow passage between towering walls. But he also saw something else: an option. Could one integrate the spiritual and the rational? The communal and the individual? He believed it could be done. His philosophy was not an attempt at sewing two mutually exclusive realities into one, no. It was much subtler, much riskier – it was integration.

Literature Analysis and Methodology

In Poola Tirupati Raju’s comparative philosophy, literature analysis and methodological rigor are the key to the synthesis of the Eastern and the Western traditions. His approach is based on the analysis of the classical texts of both traditions with the help of such tools as philological, phenomenological, and psychological ones. In light of these methodologies, Raju constructs a framework to identify and analyze the common philosophical issues and responses provided by these different traditions. The philological method is the key to Raju’s comparative work. This method involves the analysis and interpretation of texts from the past with focus on the language, culture and history of the texts. Thus, Raju shows how thinkers of different civilizations – be it Athenian or Indian – have struggled with the same ontological and cosmological issues. He uses the Upanishads [11], Śaṅkara’s [6] works, Aristotle’s *Nicomachean Ethics* [8], Heidegger’s *Being and Time* [4], and others to demonstrate that there is a commonality in the search for meaning and the understanding of the self. Phenomenology, especially comparative phenomenology of human experience, is one of the key components of Raju’s approach illustrated in his seminal work *Introduction to Comparative Philosophy* [1]. This vector enables Raju to go beyond the mere philosophical interpretation of texts to understand how various philosophical systems are practiced. It emphasizes the existence of the people who apply these philosophies and does not only concentrate on the written material but also on the real-life experience. In this way, Raju juxtaposes the human condition in the Eastern and the Western traditions – the Vedantic [3] longing for the union with the universe or the existentialist desire for meaning in the meaningless world

Discussion and Results

The integration of the Eastern and the Western philosophical systems in Poola Tirupati Raju’s work presents several discoveries that question the conventional wisdom of the dichotomy between the two systems. Raju’s elaborate comparative study effectively proves that the division between the Oriental mysticism and the Occidental reason is more of an artifact than a genuine philosophical divide. His exploration provides a direction as to how these two traditions can be harmonized and not be in opposition to each other. Thus, in the synthesis of Vedanta and

existentialism, which Raju has attempted, he tries to link the Eastern concept of self-fulfilment with the Western concept of freedom. Vedanta speaks of the self-effacement in the cosmic self and existentialism is concerned with the individual's search for meaning in a meaningless universe. Raju argues that both traditions ultimately address the same existential question: What is the nature of the self and how does one reconcile oneself to one's position in the cosmos? His findings indicate that self-fulfillment in the Vedantic tradition does not mean the denial of individuality; instead, it leads to the integration of the individual into the cosmic whole, as existentialism aims at finding one's true self and being free in the process. The other major finding of Raju's comparative study is his attempt to compare Buddhism with Western phenomenology. Phenomenology is concerned with the experience of the world and Buddhism, especially in its message of suffering and change, is a good fit. Both traditions aim at explaining the nature of human existence in a world that is ever in a state of flux. Raju's analysis shows that despite the fact that these two schools originate from two completely different cultures, they both address the core of human existence – the problem of transience. In his work, this parallel becomes a fertile ground for continued conversation between Buddhist metaphysics and phenomenological investigation, which indicates that the human experience is the same across cultures.

To attempt such a synthesis is not without risk. Philosophy, after all, is rooted in the soil of its birthplace. Eastern thought, flourishing in the rich lands of introspection and metaphysical wonder, cannot easily be grafted onto the rational, almost mechanical gardens of Western philosophy. But Raju was undeterred. He ventured into this difficult terrain with tools both old and new. And with these tools, he tried to shape a bridge between the two great minds of humanity Raju's philological method [1, 299], for instance, was like peeling back the layers of a long-forgotten text, a text written not just in words but in the very fabric of human experience. Through these ancient words, he sought to reveal the common roots of disparate systems, showing how the concerns of an Athenian philosopher might mirror those of a sage in the high mountains of India. His phenomenology was something altogether different. It wasn't

about what was said but what was felt, what was experienced. He sought to dive into the lived realities of those who walked these philosophical paths. And his psychological approach — here we see the true brilliance of his mind—he knew that thought does not exist in a vacuum. It is shaped by the fears, the desires, the hopes of the people who dare to think it. But what was the result of all this labor? It was not merely a comparison of thoughts. Raju sought to bring them into conversation, into a kind of hesitant dialogue where each tradition could find its own reflection in the other’s words. Indian philosophy, especially the Vedānta and the highest forms of Buddhism, admitted the possibility of the mind’s coming together, not only into a mass, but into a conscious unity, in which it can experience the great conscious unity of the universe and beyond it. It referred to the grand conscious unity by the name of God, Absolute, Brahman, Vijñāna, Tathatā, Nirvāṇa and so on. In western philosophy also, the Neo-Platonists, the great Christian mystics and some of the idealistic philosophers realized the truth of this statement. Then the problem is posed for philosophy: How is that great unity, the One, the Advaita, to be related to the world of plurality? The unity is timeless and spaceless and is therefore everlasting; the plurality is in time and space and is therefore temporal. Impermanence is because of process and its last extremity, which science and philosophy have discovered up to now, is matter made up of fleeting occurrences of energy, force. It is the extremity of the outwardness of human life, man’s consciousness. The great unity is the negation of inwardness and is a unity of all the fleeting occurrences of spatial and temporal expansion [1,310]. Consider, for instance, Vedanta and existentialism. On the surface, they seem to speak different languages. One, a language of unity, of dissolving into the eternal. The other, a language of separation, of standing alone in the abyss of freedom. And yet, Raju saw that they were both trying to grapple with the same thing—the self, and its place in the world. Or take his comparison of Buddhism and phenomenology. The former, ancient and wise, speaks of suffering, of impermanence. The latter, modern and meticulous, examines experience in all its fleeting forms. But both, in their own way, ask the same question: what does it mean to live in a world where nothing is certain, where everything fades? Raju saw this,

and in seeing it, he opened a doorway. He allowed these two ways of thinking to enter one another's worlds, to recognize each other as brothers long lost in time. But more than all of this—more than the techniques, the methods, the comparisons—was Raju's belief in humanity. At the heart of everything, he believed in the value of the human experience. He believed that all these divisions, these walls built between East and West, between individual and collective, were artificial. Beneath them all, there is only the human, striving, suffering, dreaming. And it is this shared experience, this fundamental humanism, that allowed Raju to build his bridge. His approach is not simply a set of philosophical ideas. It is a roadmap. A way forward. It suggests that the fractures that divide us—cultural, intellectual, geographical—are not as deep as they seem. They can be mended through dialogue, through understanding, through the patient work of comparing, of contrasting, of synthesizing, we can build a world where these traditions do not stand in opposition but in harmony. In this way, Raju's philosophy stands as a testament to hope. In a world that grows more divided with each passing day, he offers us a vision of unity—not the forced unity of conquest or conformity, but a unity born of understanding, of mutual respect. He reminds us that the path forward is not through isolation, but through engagement. Not through separation, but through synthesis.

Conclusion

Thus, the philosophy of Poola Tirupati Raju is not only for scholars or philosophers, but for all of us. His comparative philosophy is a rebellion against the divisions that have been part of human life for so long. He enlightens us that to know the other is not to deny the self but to discover the self in a different manner. In this, his work is not just philosophical, but something more: a guide to how one might live in this world that is growing more complicated, more connected. His call for unity of the minds is not a murmur but a loud voice telling the world that we are all one people, be it East or West.

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